

Original Research

Seasonal Variation of Orthoptera Densities in Lesser Kestrel Foraging Habitats of the Thessaly Plain

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Abstract

This study investigates the seasonal variation of Orthoptera densities across the main crop types of the Thessaly Plain, central Greece, during the 2014–2015 breeding seasons of the Lesser Kestrel (*Falco naumanni*). A total of 1,820 line transects were conducted in 364 fields, yielding 5,300 Orthoptera individuals belonging mainly to the families Acrididae and Tettigoniidae. Mean densities were highest in fallow land and cereal fields, whereas cotton and maize exhibited consistently low or zero abundances, particularly during early breeding phases. Even though surveys recorded only numerical counts and not species identity or biomass, and thus the results cannot be directly converted to prey biomass, the study demonstrates the critical contribution of semi-natural habitats and crop heterogeneity to sustaining Orthoptera populations in intensively managed agroecosystems. The findings highlight the need for agri-environmental practices that maintain accessible prey throughout the Lesser Kestrel's breeding cycle.

Keywords

Biodiversity; Orthoptera; Line transects; Lesser Kestrel; Raptor

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Sezonska spremenljivost gostote kobilic (Orthoptera) v habitatih prehranjevanja južne postovke na planoti Tesalije

Izvleček

Študija preučuje sezonska nihanja gostote kobilic (Orthoptera) na področjih glavnih vrst pridelkov na planoti Tesalije v osrednji Grčiji med sezonami razmnoževanja južne postovke (*Falco naumanni*) v letih 2014–2015. Na 364 poljih je bilo opravljenih skupno 1820 linijskih transektov, kjer smo zaznali 5300 osebkov kobilic, ki so v glavnem pripadali družinam Acrididae in Tettigoniidae. Povprečne gostote kobilic so bile najvišje na pustih poljih in žitnih poljih, medtem ko so bile na bombažnih in koruznih poljih gostote dosledno nizke ali nične, zlasti v zgodnjih fazah sezon razmnoževanja. V raziskavi so bili zabeleženi le številčni podatki in ne identitete vrst ali biomase, zato rezultatov ni mogoče neposredno pretvoriti v biomaso plena. Kljub temu študija kaže na ključni prispevek polnaravnih habitatov in heterogenosti pridelkov k ohranjanju populacij kobilic v intenzivno obdelanih agroekosistemih. Ugotovitve poudarjajo potrebo po kmetijsko-okoljskih praksah, ki ohranjajo dostopnost plena skozi celoten razmnoževalni cikel južne postovke.

Ključne besede

biodiverziteta; Orthoptera; linijski transekti; južna postovka; ptica roparica

Introduction

Long-term changes of agricultural use in rural landscapes have created a mosaic of extensive open cultivation areas and smaller natural vegetation patches or corridors. These landscapes, formed primarily by agriculture, support the habitat of a significant number of species (Franco and Sutherland, 2004). At the same time, the species' well-being depends on the abundance, quality and distribution of resources needed, and thus lies on the farming practices utilised (Catry et al., 2012b). The intensification of agriculture that occurred in recent decades led to dramatic biodiversity loss in these agricultural areas, and when combined with the consequences of climate change, it greatly affected these agriculture-dependent species (Rodríguez and Wiegand, 2009). Modern agriculture poses a major threat to biodiversity, while further intensification is expected to have serious deteriorative impacts on species and habitats (Catry et al., 2012b).

These agroecosystems support many bird species currently under Unfavourable Conservation Status in Europe (European Environmental Agency 2021). Many farmland bird species of southern Europe—including *Otis tarda*, *Tetrax tetrax*, *Pterocles orientalis*, and *Falco naumanni*—have experienced severe declines, largely driven by habitat loss and degradation resulting from rapid agricultural change (Franco & Sutherland, 2004). Habitat het-

erogeneity and food availability are key drivers of farmland bird diversity in intensively farmed landscapes, showing positive relationships between landscape complexity and bird species richness (Holoskova et al., 2025). The way in which these species populations adapt to habitat quality and quantity decline is a major concern of conservation biology (Sánchez-Zapata et al., 2003). Therefore, understanding habitat-species relationships and the impact of changing landscape characteristics on the species is critical for understanding the causes behind their observed population declines (Catry et al., 2012a).

The Lesser Kestrel is a colonial migratory raptor. It is a species with familiarity to human activities, also considered a useful farmer ally in pest management (Kmetova et al., 2012). It usually nests in holes and crevices of old buildings, and its breeding habitats are the fairly flat agricultural landscapes of the Western Palearctic (Cramp et al., 1992; Parr et al., 1995; Negro, 1997; Perez et al., 2011). Breeding colonies are mostly located within cities and villages surrounded by large, agricultural landscapes (Bustamante, 1997; Franco et al., 2005; Perez et al., 2011; Gradev et al., 2023).

Its populations have declined rapidly in Western Europe, corresponding to a 46% loss every decade since 1950 (Mihoub et al., 2010). For this reason, it had been classified as "globally threatened" by the IUCN (Collar & Andrew, 1988). Since the 1990s, the European populations of the species have shown an increasing trend, and today the

species is classified as "Stable" (BirdLife International, 2021). The Greek population was considered "Vulnerable" (Legakis & Maragou, 2009) until 2013, when it was reclassified as "Least Concern" (LC) (NECCA, 2024). Its population decline is mainly attributed to the intensification of agricultural practices (Donazar et al., 1993; Parr et al., 1995; Bustamante, 1997; Tella et al., 1998; Tella & Forero, 2000; BirdLife International, 2004), as Lesser Kestrels depend on the conservation of the agricultural mosaic (Catry et al., 2012a).

The species forages in open areas with low vegetation (Cramp et al., 1992; Negro, 1997) where it preys mainly upon invertebrates (Parr et al., 1997), which constitute up to 85-94% of its diet and small mammals (Tella et al., 1996; Christakis & Sfougaris, 2025). In Thessaly, the majority of the Lesser Kestrel's diet during its pre-breeding period mainly consists of Coleoptera prey, while during breeding and post-breeding period the species feeds mainly on Orthoptera (Christakis et al., 2023). In terms of biomass, Orthoptera constitutes the most important invertebrate prey category.

Species of the Orthoptera order have traditionally been considered pests by farmers as they are mostly herbivorous, yet they constitute an important part of the diets of many species, such as farmland birds - including the Lesser Kestrel, thus controlling their populations (Belovsky & Slade, 1993). Important factors determining Orthoptera diversity and dispersal are vegetation structure and microclimate,

while temperature is the main physiological regulating factor (Willott, 1997; Marini et al., 2008). Orthoptera populations in the agroecosystem are affected by insecticides, intensive mowing, fire and grazing. Furthermore, vast areas with monocultures are undesirable as Orthoptera need grasslands or natural vegetation for egg laying and feeding during their nymphal stages, thus uncultivated field margins are favourable (Wilson et al., 1999; Badenhauer et al., 2012).

The aim of this study was to quantify Orthoptera densities across the main cultivation types of the Thessalian plain, which are the main feeding habitats for 65-70% of the total Greek Lesser Kestrel population, and assess their seasonal variation relevant to the species breeding period.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted in the eastern Thessaly plain, central Greece, within an intensively cultivated landscape of ~150 km² surrounding the settlements of Stefanovikeio and Rizomylos—important Lesser Kestrel colonies. The area is dominated by arable crops such as cereals, legumes, cotton, maize, and fallow land (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The study area

Slika 1. Območje študije

Line transects as a method for estimating Orthoptera abundance

The Line transect method is a cheap and fast yet efficient way to count Orthoptera and is widely used to estimate the density, abundance and richness of the families Acrididae and Tettigoniidae. When carried out in open areas with low vegetation (<50cm plant height) and the density of Orthoptera is relatively low (<2 adults/m²), the method delivers accurate results (Gardiner et al., 2005).

To perform the line transects, the observer walks along a predetermined straight path within the selected area, counting individuals of the species under study. In the case of Orthoptera, all observed individuals, both stationary and moving, are counted (Isern-Vallverdu et al., 1993). The transects should be as straight as possible, parallel, and without overlapping segments. The distance between each transect should be consistent and predetermined throughout the experiment. Also, the speed of the transects should be consistent and not too slow, to reduce the probability of double-counting individuals (Greenwood & Robinson, 2006). Orthoptera movements depend on several factors, such as temperature, rain, wind, life cycle stage and height and density of vegetation, so an underestimation of Orthoptera population density is possible due to non-observation. All transects of each experiment should be performed, if possible, in similar, favourable environmental conditions (Isern-Vallverdu et al., 1993). To estimate the density of the

population under study, the following equation is used: $D = n/2La$, where D is the density of individuals per area unit (individuals/m²), n is the number of individuals counted by transects, L is the total length of each transect (m) and a is the half of the width of the strip area of active counting while performing each line transect (Krebs 2014).

Orthoptera counts

Line transects took place in three distinct periods of the seasonal presence of the Lesser Kestrel in Thessaly, in order to investigate Orthoptera abundance. The periods chosen, reflect important phases for the species breeding season: 1) Arrivals and pair formation (late March to early May), 2) Incubation of eggs and chick rearing /Breeding (mid-May to late June), 3) Nest abandonment / Pre-migratory phase (July and August).

Within the study area, 20 random sampling stations were selected using a Geographical Information System (GIS). A minimum distance of 500m between stations was set to cover the whole extent of the study area. For each station, the nearest available field of each crop type (cereal, legumes, cotton, maize, fallow land) was identified and tagged for repeated surveys. Line transects throughout the study were conducted in these fields (Fig. 2).

During two consecutive years for each study phase, five line transects, at a steady predefined walking pace, 50 meters long, 10 meters apart and 10 meters away from the

Figure 2. The 20 selected random points in the study area.

Slika 2. 20 naključno izbranih točk vzorčenja na območju študije.

field edges, were carried out in each selected field. The effective strip width was set to 1 m (0.5 m on each side of the observer), following Gardiner et al. (2005), who recommend narrow widths in low vegetation to maximise detection accuracy. The recordings concerned mostly families of Acrididae and Tettigoniidae. Vegetation height was roughly measured, and numerous testing transects were performed by the researchers to compensate for the varied detectability of Orthoptera among crops, particularly in tall vegetation. Similarly to O'Neill & Rolston (2007), who showed that grasshoppers are active and detectable only when environmental temperatures allow them to thermo-regulate effectively, and in agreement with standard scouting protocols recommending surveys at temperatures ≥ 21 °C (Rodbell et al. 2005), fieldwork was performed during hours of high Orthoptera mobility (10 am to 8 pm local time) and in any case at a temperature ≥ 20 °C (Rodriguez and Bustamante, 2008).

Because data lacked normality and homogeneity, differences among crop types and study phases were evaluated using Kruskal–Wallis tests followed by Mann–Whitney pairwise comparisons. Multiple comparison corrections were not applied due to the exploratory nature of the study. Tables, graphs and statistical analysis of the data were created and performed using Microsoft Excel 365, IBM Statistics v.25 and PAST (v.4.02).

Results

A total of 1,820 line transects were carried out during orthoptera population density estimations, in 364 fields (5 Line transects/field) during the two years of the study (2014 and 2015), and a total of 5,300 orthoptera individuals were counted (mean=2.91, S.D.=8.55 individuals per line transect). Across all crops and years, fallow land supported the highest mean Orthoptera densities (8.31 ± 0.73 individuals per transect), followed by cereals (4.07 ± 0.46). Cotton and maize consistently exhibited near-zero counts during early phases. Maize transects could not be conducted during the second and mostly the third study phases in either year because vegetation height and density prevented visibility, resulting in reduced sample sizes.

The results presented in tables 1, 2 and 3 show the recordings for every crop type and study phase of the study. Furthermore, Figure 3 presents the mean Orthoptera individuals/m² recorded for each crop type.

In the first year of the study (2014), the highest number of Orthoptera per line transect was recorded during the first study phase (5.37 ± 0.76). In contrast, in 2015, the peak number of individuals per line transect was observed during the third study phase (4.24 ± 0.60). A non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences in mean Orthoptera counts across the study period ($H = 149.8$, $p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the mean number of Orthoptera individuals counted in fallow fields was the highest among all crop types (8.31 ± 0.73) during the study, followed by cereal crops (4.07 ± 0.46). Statistically significant differences were observed among the different crop types, as determined by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($H = 451.237$, $p < 0.05$).

During the first study phase in 2014, Orthoptera were not detected at all in cotton or maize fields. On the contrary, the mean number of individuals recorded per line transect was 11.35 ± 2.17 in cereal fields and 7.46 ± 1.35 in fallow land. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences among crop types during this phase ($H = 32.44$, $p < 0.05$). In the second phase of the study in 2014, Orthoptera were not detected in cotton fields, except for two instances where a single individual was observed. Conversely, a mean of 6.75 ± 1.14 Orthoptera per line transect was counted in fallow land. The Kruskal-Wallis test indicated statistically significant differences in Orthoptera counts across crop types ($H = 55.58$, $p < 0.05$). During the third study phase of 2014, the mean number of Orthoptera per line transect was 6.52 ± 1.04 in fallow land, followed by 2.69 ± 0.60 in cereal fields. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed statistically significant differences in Orthoptera abundance among crop types ($H = 61.15$, $p < 0.05$).

Similarly, in the first study phase of 2015, Orthoptera were not detected in cotton or maize fields, while the mean number of individuals per line transect was 1.36 ± 0.254 in cereal fields and 0.8 ± 0.19 in fallow land. Statistically significant differences were detected ($H = 13.99$, $p < 0.05$). During the second study phase of 2015, the mean number of individuals per line transect was 13.68 ± 3.01 in fallow land and 1.24 ± 0.36 in cereal fields. No Orthoptera were recorded in cotton fields in this study phase. The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed statistically significant differences in Orthoptera counts between crop types ($H = 92.03$, $p < 0.05$). In the third study phase of 2015, the mean number of Orthoptera per line transect was 6.52 ± 1.04 in fallow land and 2.69 ± 0.60 in cereal fields. The Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed statistically significant differences during this phase ($H = 125.8$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 1. The number of line transects carried out, and the mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect were recorded for all crop types of the study.

Tabela 1. Število izvedenih linijskih transektov in povprečno število posameznih osebkov redu Orthoptera na linijski transekt, zabeleženo za vse vrste pridelkov v študiji.

Crop type	2014			2015		
	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error
Cereal	295	5,89	0,82	260	2,01	0,26
Cotton	235	0,43	0,07	260	0,14	0,03
Fallow	170	6,95	0,70	140	9,96	1,36
Legumes	200	1,19	0,13	185	0,44	0,09
Maize	40	0,10	0,05	35	0,11	0,07

Table 2. Number of line transects carried out and mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect recorded for all phases of the study (1. Arrivals and pair formation, 2. Incubation of eggs and chick rearing /Breeding, 3. Nest abandonment / Pre-migratory phase).

Tabela 2. Število izvedenih linijskih transektov in povprečno število posameznih osebkov redu Orthoptera na linijski transekt, zabeleženo za vse faze študije (1. Prihodi in tvorba parov, 2. Inkubacija jajc in vzreja mladičev/razmnoževanje, 3. Zapuščenje gnezd/predmigracijska faza).

Study Phase	2014			2015		
	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error
1	330	3,47	0,30	310	0,60	0,09
2	310	5,37	0,76	295	2,32	0,50
3	300	2,48	0,32	275	4,24	0,60
Total	940	3,47	0,30	880	2,40	0,26

Table 3. Number of line transects and mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect recorded for all phases and crop types of the study.

Tabela 3. Število linijskih transektov in povprečno število posameznih osebkov redu Orthoptera na linijski transekt, zabeleženo za vse faze in vrste pridelkov v študiji.

Crop type/ Study Phase	2014			2015		
	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error	No of line transects	Mean Orthoptera individuals per line transect	Standard Error
Pair formation						
Cereal	100	11,35	2,17	90	1,36	0,25
Cotton	65	0,00	0,00	80	0,00	0,00
Fallow	65	7,46	1,35	55	0,80	0,19
Legumes	70	2,16	0,27	65	0,32	0,11
Maize	30	0,00	0,00	20	0,00	0,00
Incubation of eggs and chick rearing						
Cereal	100	3,47	0,64	90	1,24	0,36
Cotton	80	0,03	0,02	90	0,00	0,00
Fallow	55	6,75	1,14	40	13,68	3,01
Legumes	65	0,68	0,18	60	0,37	0,15
Maize	10	0,40	0,16	15	0,27	0,15
Nest abandonment / Pre-migratory						
Cereal	95	2,69	0,60	80	3,61	0,67
Cotton	90	1,09	0,16	90	0,40	0,07
Fallow	50	6,52	1,04	45	17,84	2,64
Legumes	65	0,65	0,14	60	0,65	0,21
Maize	0	0,00	0,00	0	0,00	0,00

Figure 3. Mean Orthoptera individuals/m² and sample sizes (number of line transects) for all crop types of the total duration of the study.

Slika 3. Povprečno število posameznih osebkov redju Orthoptera na m² in velikost vzorcev (število linijskih transektov) za vse vrste pridelkov v celotnem obdobju študije.

Discussion

This study investigated Orthoptera densities in the main crop fields of the study area (cereal, cotton, maize and legume crops and fallow land), which constitute the main foraging habitats of the Lesser Kestrel, during its breeding season in Thessaly. A recent study in the same area highlighted fallow land, legumes and cereals as the selected foraging habitats by the species (Christakis & Sfougaris, 2021).

Orthoptera counts via line transects showed that during the breeding season of the Lesser Kestrel, fallow/uncultivated fields and to a lesser extent cereals maintained the largest Orthoptera populations, while in legume fields (mainly alfalfa), fewer individuals were recorded, indicating greater Acrididae and Tettigoniidae families abundance in fallow/uncultivated and cereal fields. The finding that cereals in the study area were richer in Orthoptera than legumes is in agreement with Olfert et al. (1995), who suggested that the biotic potential of locusts is highest in wheat cultivation than legume crops (such as lentils and peas). Cereal crops seem to support a wide variety of large

insects, including Lepidoptera larvae and several Orthoptera (Stoate et al., 2000), while Orthoptera species, mainly of the Acrididae family, are considered cereal crop pests (Habtewold & Landin, 1992). Nevertheless, in all three phases during both years of the study, Orthoptera were recorded in these three crop types, while they were absent from cotton during the first two phases and appeared in small numbers in the third phase in both years. The minimal or no plant cover of cotton fields during the period before the breeding phase (second phase of the study) is a prohibitive factor for herbivorous insect species, such as Orthoptera, justifying their absence from these fields. The third study phase was characterised by the appearance of Orthoptera in all types of crops studied, since in all cases, plant cover was apparent.

In this study, Orthoptera densities can be characterised as relatively low, even in most of the fallow land, except for some fallow fields, where Orthoptera were counted at relatively high densities. However, the plant species heterogeneity of fallow/uncultivated fields reflects the Orthoptera densities recorded, which vary strongly among the different

fields of this type. These variations can be attributed to the different structure and composition of the vegetation in each fallow: fields with more grass and dense plant cover maintained increased numbers of Orthoptera, in contrast to fields dominated by perennials, broad-leaved or woody plants, where fewer Orthoptera were counted. Plant communities have a significant impact on the populations and density of Orthoptera, as they are related to the quantity and quality of their food (De Wysiecki et al., 2011). The higher densities of Orthoptera in semi-natural environments such as meadows, fallow lands and uncultivated margins, compared to other types of cultivated habitats, are confirmed by Rodriguez and Bustamante (2008), who also positively correlated Orthoptera density with the vegetative cover of the field and negatively with the increase in its size. The great heterogeneity that these systems exhibit, in terms of vegetation structure and density, probably makes some of them locally and temporally unsuitable foraging grounds for the Lesser Kestrel. Therefore, part of these habitats may be rich in unapproachable prey items, due to high and dense vegetation. Nevertheless, fallow/uncultivated fields continue to be important habitats around Kestrel colonies, functioning as shelters and reservoirs of potential prey for the species, from which surrounding areas/crops can be enriched.

The study results suggest that the most important type of farmland for the Lesser Kestrel in terms of Orthoptera (Acrididae and Tettigoniidae families) prey abundance is fallow land, confirming the opportunistic foraging strategy of the species, since fallow land seems to be the most preferred foraging habitat by the species in the area (Christakis & Sfougaris, 2021). Given that food availability is perhaps the most decisive controlling factor for any bird population, as prey scarcity at any stage of the breeding season can reduce the species' reproductive success, data on prey abundance and availability around colonies at each stage of the Kestrel breeding season is of imperative importance. In general, arthropod biomass and abundance seem to decrease with increasing agricultural intensification, likely limiting prey for dependent farmland birds (González del Portillo et al., 2021). Moreover, research on the diet of a declining species, such as the Lesser Kestrel, is of vital importance for its conservation and protection (Kopij, 2002). Based on such data, it is possible to manage the agroecosystem in favour of the species, avoiding a lack of food resources during its breeding season (Franco & Sutherland, 2004). Examples of Lesser Kestrel - friendly agroecosystem management and farming practices include the promotion

of crop rotation and fallowing, the promotion of low-input crops such as cereals, the conservation of traditional agricultural practices and the protection of natural vegetation patches and heterogeneous mosaics in rural landscapes.

The differences in Orthoptera counts between the two study years can be attributed to interannual temperature fluctuations, as higher spring temperatures began later during the second year of the study. Although this pattern is consistent with the findings of Geppert et al. (2021), who identified temperature as the primary driver of Orthoptera population density, this explanation remains hypothetical in the context of the present study.

It should be noted that, as vegetation structure was only roughly measured, and detectability varied among crop types, particularly in tall crops, some prey-rich fallow fields may have been undercounted due to dense vegetation. Furthermore, during the second and mainly the third study phases, plant height and density in maize cultivations were prohibitive for transecting within the fields during the sampling phases (in both years of the study), resulting in a small number of line transects conducted, only during the first phase and for both years of the study. Nevertheless, maize cultivations are not favourable Lesser Kestrel foraging habitats as accessibility to prey is the major foraging habitat selection factor (Donazar et al., 1993; Rodriguez et al., 2014). Moreover, because only numbers of individuals were recorded—not species identity or size—results cannot be used to estimate prey biomass, which is the most relevant metric for Lesser Kestrel foraging ecology. Orthoptera size can vary depending on their age class, and given that the Lesser Kestrel selects its prey, especially during the chick-rearing period, based on biomass, improving hunting efficiency (Christakis et al., 2023), to estimate the available prey at the biomass level, the sizes and species of Orthoptera should be further recorded. Future studies should incorporate biomass estimates to refine habitat management recommendations. However, this study constitutes a basis for investigating in depth the species' foraging ecology and agricultural biodiversity.

Conclusions

This study provides the first systematic assessment of Orthoptera densities across the main crop types of the Thessaly Plain during the Lesser Kestrel breeding season. Recordings were carried out using the line transect method

in the main crop fields of the study area, including cereals, cotton, legumes, maize cultivations and fallow/uncultivated land. The results showed that fallow land and cereal crops maintained the highest abundance of Orthoptera, while cotton and maize crops showed significantly lower or no densities. The heterogeneity of vegetation decisively affects the presence of Orthoptera, with the highest concentrations being found in fields with rich vegetation cover. Furthermore, the lack of herbivorous insects in cotton fields, mostly during early pair formation of the Lesser Kestrel, seems to make them unsuitable for foraging habitat for the Lesser Kestrel concerning Orthoptera prey, mostly Acrididae and Tettigoniidae families. On the contrary, uncultivated areas function as critical habitats, ensuring the availability of this prey. Although Orthoptera densities were thoroughly quantified, the absence of species- and size-level data limits biomass interpretation. Future research integrating species identity, size classes, and biomass measurements will further improve our understanding of prey availability for the Lesser Kestrel. Nevertheless, the findings of this study highlight the importance of maintaining semi-natural patches and crop diversification in maintaining populations of predators, such as the Lesser Kestrel.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, C.C. and A.S.; methodology, C.C. and A.S.; writing—original draft preparation, C.C.; writing—review and editing, C.C. and A.S.; visualization, C.C.; supervision, A.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical and Access Permissions

The study involved non-invasive visual surveys and required no handling of animals. Access to private fields was granted by landowners. No additional permits were required.

Data Availability

Research data of this study were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18337395>).

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